

Date of publication xxxx 00, 0000, date of current version xxxx 00, 0000.

Digital Object Identifier XX.YYYY/ACCESS.2019.DOI

Scalable prediction of service-level events in datacenter infrastructure using deep neural networks

ALBERTO MOZO¹, ITAI SEGALL², UDI MARGOLIN³ and SANDRA GÓMEZ-CANAVAL⁴

¹Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (e-mail: a.mozo@upm.es)

²Nokia Bell Labs - NJ, US (e-mail: itai.segall@nokia-bell-labs.com)

³Nokia - IL (email: udi.margolin@nokia.com)

⁴Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (e-mail: sm.gomez@upm.es)

Corresponding author: A. Mozo (e-mail: a.mozo@upm.es).

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union under the H2020 grant agreement n. 671625 (project CogNet).

ABSTRACT

The complexity of cloud datacenter scenarios poses new challenges in infrastructure management processes such as the impracticality of collecting specific service level events from inside the datacenter infrastructure, and the scalability issues that can appear during event monitoring when thousands of virtual machines have to be polled at a granularity of seconds. Therefore, it would be desirable to provide mechanisms for obtaining these types of events without incurring in the previously described problems. To this end, we propose a generic and scalable method based on the application of deep neural network architectures for predicting service level events using only a reduced number of generic datacenter infrastructure statistics that can be monitored in a scalable way.

We demonstrate in a controlled scenario of a real datacenter and using only three variables from a physical machine that it is possible to predict events in real-time and with decent accuracy, without needing to deploy any meter in the end-user equipment. Specifically, we demonstrate this over two service-level events: i) the so-called Noisy Neighbors effect, a harmful situation that appears in physical machines due to the interferences created by the interaction of virtual machines running on them; and ii) the jitter values of a multimedia call running in a virtual machine.

We set up a testbed in a real datacenter deploying physical and virtual machines, running a large amount of different experiments for 1000 hours and collecting samples at a 10 seconds granularity in a dataset of 260,000 records. Two different scenarios, in which training and testing data sets contain significant statistical differences, are deployed to demonstrate a better generalization ability of deep models in changing scenarios when compared with traditional Machine Learning techniques. A set of different deep architectures are proposed for both use cases and approximately 4,000 deep models were trained and tested. In both use cases, the best deep models show a good performance when predicting service level events, even if the inputs do not exactly follow the statistical patterns of the data used during training.

INDEX TERMS datacenters, cloud computing, performance evaluation, deep learning, noisy neighbors, jitter, classification models, regression models.

I. INTRODUCTION

INTERNET communications are more and more based on Cloud infrastructures deployed in specialized telecom datacenters, which combine the flexibility of today's computing clouds with the service quality of telecom systems. Nowadays, Cloud datacenters are exposed to a continuous

growth of the Internet traffic that will increase exponentially due to current and forthcoming 5G deployments – analysts predict that in the short term 90% of Internet traffic will go through datacenters [1].

Virtualization is utilised in datacenters as the key technology to provide flexibility to the diversity of applications

running on top of them. In particular, Cloud infrastructures use virtualization as the mechanism to provide performance isolation between multiple application services. Each application service is typically allocated within one or more virtual machines (VM) or containers. While this provides logical isolation for each tenant, sharing of physical resources (including internal networking, network bandwidth, CPU, memory or cache) is limiting this isolation [16]. Application malfunctioning translates directly into end-users discouraged from using the application, or cloud providers compensating the client for SLA (Service Level Agreement) violations. In this context, some of the key challenges for the execution of real-time and high performance cloud applications are poor network performance and quality of service, virtualization overhead causing performance degradation, and noisy neighbor issues [5] among others. In particular, it is crucial for datacenter infrastructures to provide predictable and deterministic Quality of Service (QoS) to applications in terms of key service-level metrics such as rejection rate, mean time between failures, response time, throughput, packet latency and jitter, financial cost, or energy consumption [17]. QoS management deals with the problem of allocating network and infrastructure resources to applications running in VMs (or containers) in order to guarantee a high level of service including performance and availability. In general, a combination of different techniques such as scheduling, admission control and dynamic resource provisioning are utilised for providing QoS to applications running in a datacenter [4].

Due to the size and complexity of modern cloud datacenters, it is not unusual that service assurance and QoS management systems find that it is impractical for QoS management systems to collect some types of service-level metrics and events from inside its infrastructure (e.g. obtaining the jitter values of a multimedia application running in a VM). Additionally, scalability issues can appear during event monitoring when hundred of thousands of virtual machines have to be polled at a granularity of seconds (e.g. gathering the CPU load values of all virtual machines in a datacenter). Furthermore, predicting the performance of cloud services is intrinsically hard as such services involve large and complex software systems that run on general-purpose systems, which do not provide realtime guarantees. Therefore, it would be desirable to provide new mechanisms to datacenter management systems for predicting such service-level metrics and events using scalable and practical approaches.

In this context we address two different use cases in this paper. Firstly, we research the application of machine learning and in particular deep learning techniques to predict a harmful service-level event called the Noisy Neighbor effect that not only raises scalability problems but also requires nontrivial mechanisms in order to be detected with a decent accuracy. Our proposal sets up a realistic scenario in a real datacenter and deploys on it different deep neural network architectures to demonstrate that it is possible to detect this harmful event with accuracy and to differentiate it from a typical overload situation where not enough resources were

assigned to a VM to begin with. Predictions will be done using as input only a small set of infrastructure variables not related with the event to be detected. Secondly, we propose the application of machine learning models and deep learning architectures for predicting the jitter values of a multimedia application using the same set of infrastructure variables utilised in the first use case. Usually, this service-level metric is obtained by adding ad-hoc meters at the ends of the communication path (e.g. installing and running an application in end-user equipments) which can be unfeasible to deploy in many real scenarios. The added value of our proposal is to provide QoS management systems with an equivalent mechanism based on machine learning for predicting these values from inside the datacenter infrastructure, without deploying any application in end-user equipments and using only a small set of infrastructure variables not related with the metric. It is worth noting that, in both use cases, the proposed machine learning methods are scalable and service-agnostic in the sense that they take as input the same small number of datacenter infrastructure variables instead of specific service-level metrics.

In addition, we research the advantages of using complex deep learning architectures against traditional machine learning models for providing trained models with better generalization capabilities. To this end, models will be tested against scenarios statistically different from the ones used during training in order to demonstrate a superior generalization ability of deep models in realistic deployments when predicting in changing scenarios.

A. RELATED WORK

The problem of predicting metrics with machine learning techniques in cloud and network environments has raised researchers' attention during the last decade. Techniques for predicting many different types of service-level metrics and events such as TCP throughput rates [34], the probability of image failures [35], and the response times of web applications [36], [37] have been proposed. All these works predict a specific service-level metric selecting a small number of observation variables (features) related to the service-level metric, which could raise scalability issues as the number of different services grows. In [32] authors consider all available features in a cloud and network environment, which can be thousands, suggesting a more general approach as feature selection is not guided by the specific metric to predict. However, if the number of utilised features is high, scalability issues can appear when collecting data at a small granularity. In a posterior work [33] the same authors limited the number of selected features and simplified the scenario to only two physical machines where virtual machines were not used, which is far from a real datacenter scenario. Common to all these works is that they do not take into account the temporal relationships that are present in consecutive samples and can be extracted using adequate neural network architectures such as LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) and 1-D Convolutional networks.

1) Noisy Neighbors

Considering that not all users utilise at the same time the total capacity of resources they previously reserved, it is a common practise to increase the overall utilization of datacenter infrastructure applying overbooking techniques [9]. In this context, the available resource capacity in a physical machine cannot be enough for several VMs (or containers) allocated in it and therefore they compete for the same resources what may cause overload and resource contention bottlenecks with a noticeable degradation of performance as a result [6]. Even in absence of overbooking, and due to a lack of strong VM isolation with virtualization, the so-called Noisy neighbor effect can appear when the resource capacity in a physical machine is enough for the allocated VMs but its performance is degraded because the applications running in VMs interfere when competing for resources such as CPU, main memory or network I/O [8]. A prompt detection of degradation is important for infrastructure management systems in order to allow them to take proactive decisions for reallocating resources dynamically in the cloud infrastructure.

In particular, a priori detection of the specific factor causing the performance degradation (noisy neighbors, overload, etc) is crucial for taking the pertinent actions to optimally reallocate the affected VMs within the cloud infrastructure that will avoid a negative impact on the QoS perceived by applications. Since the decision to be taken by the infrastructure manager in order to solve a noisy neighbor or an overload situation is totally different, it is worth noting that the problem becomes more complex when we need to differentiate between a noisy neighbor effect or an overload situation where not enough resources are assigned to a VM to begin with. Unfortunately, the detection of noisy neighbors is not a trivial problem and its differentiation from the classic overload situation is a current research challenge.

Some authors have proposed to model noisy neighbor interferences as performance anomalies exhibiting some kind of resource contention bottleneck. Therefore, the anomaly can be monitored using available resource metrics (e.g. CPU time, memory usage, I/O bandwidth) and the detection method applies heuristic-based techniques like simple thresholding approaches, statistical analysis from a previous known state or a set of rules [19]. These approaches exhibit well known limitations such as the fact that they lead to sub-optimal results, do not exploit the temporal nature of the data and do not distinguish the specific type of anomaly. Therefore, and due to these limitations, the application of these techniques in real scenarios is discouraged. Other works [13], [14] investigated how scheduling algorithms can detect patterns of conflicting resource usage in two applications and therefore, schedule them in order that they do not share any resources. Common to all these works is that they only apply traditional statistical learning methods and so they do not consider the usage of modern deep learning techniques that can attain much better performance in complex scenarios such these.

In order to alleviate the noisy neighbor problem, a thor-

ough analysis on the impact that VMs have on each other should be done. In addition, the decisions on VMs placement and the resources to be shared among them must be taken with care. Several works have modelled VMs placement as a multi-dimensional optimization problem that can be solved applying specific heuristics [8], [9]. Complementary, a work based on the application of fuzzy logic for safe VM placement and noisy neighbor avoidance was recently proposed in [7]. In [12] authors propose to leave some datacenter capacity unused in the underlying infrastructure in order to provide with free resources to the applications that start suffering the noisy neighbor effect. However, this approach goes in the opposite direction of current datacenter trends that make an extensive use of oversubscribing.

The inherent complexity of the noisy neighbor detection problem jointly with the dynamic and changing scenario of modern datacenters and the impossibility in many occasions of having a labeled training dataset make this problem not broadly explored using supervised machine learning techniques. To the best of our knowledge the first work applying these techniques for detecting the presence of noisy neighbors in datacenter infrastructures was proposed in [2] by the authors. However, this work presented a rather simplistic scenario in which only noisy neighbors were considered and so no differentiation was made to detect them separately from overload situations. In addition, only a small number of rather simplified experiments were run and Support Vector Machine and Random Forest models were applied attaining decent levels of accuracy. An extension of this seminal work was proposed in [1], in which Convolutional Neural Networks were applied for exploiting the time series nature of the collected data which slightly improved the results obtained in the previous paper. The Noisy Neighbors use case proposed in our manuscript can be considered as an extension of these previous works but proposing a more realistic and complex scenario, running new experiments that produced a new dataset, and training more complex neural network architectures – the number of experiments, dataset records and trained models are roughly one order of magnitude greater than the ones obtained in the previous works –. Recently, an unsupervised online algorithm for detecting anomalies in VMs or containers –considering the noisy neighbor effect as an interference problem– was proposed in [3]. This work modelled the resource usage of an application as a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) without needing any previous information about the anomaly or labeled data. However, this method can be more prone to miss the anomalies (e.g. noisy neighbor or overload effects) and cannot differentiate a noisy neighbor effect from an overload situation that as previously commented precludes its application in real datacenters.

2) Jitter prediction

Low-level QoS parameters such as bandwidth, jitter, delays and packet losses drive auto-configuration of QoE-aware adaptive applications. A diversity of research works have recently proposed the application of machine learning mod-

els (e.g. SVM, Decision Trees, Random Forest and Fully connected neural networks) for mapping subjective QoE metrics from a given QoS ([38], [39], [40], [41], [42]). Complementary, some works have researched the application of machine learning for predicting QoS such as web service QoS metrics in [43] and [44]. In particular, low level QoS values have traditionally been obtained by data collection services that monitor and gather the required data from the applications, and the network and cloud infrastructures. To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first attempt to predict a service-level QoS metric, such as jitter, using only generic infrastructure variables instead of monitoring it directly.

B. CONTRIBUTION

We propose a scalable and generic method based on deep neural networks for predicting service level events in a data-center infrastructure taking as input only a reduced number of physical machine statistics. The approach scales adequately with respect to the number of virtual machines under analysis as we only need to sample three variables gathered from physical machines instead of collecting for each service-level event a specific set of metrics that have to be sampled from applications or virtual machines. As the three variables (CPU usage, Inbound network traffic and Outbound network traffic) are collected from physical machines, the independence from the specific service events to be predicted is guaranteed while simultaneously reducing model computation time due to the tiny dimensionality of the input. Moreover, the same three variables can be used for predicting different service level events, and therefore it is not needed to collect different sets of variables for each service-level event predictor.

A set of deep learning architectures were proposed for predicting two useful service level events. Firstly, we aimed at predicting the so-called noisy neighbors effect that can appear when virtual machines that are running in the same physical machine compete for physical machine resources creating bad interferences that produce noticeable performance degradation in the system. It is worth noting that trained models can clearly differentiate this event from overload situations that imply totally different actuations in real datacenter scenarios. Secondly, and using the same realistic scenario and input variables, we predict the jitter values of a VoIP call deployed in a virtual machine that is running in the datacenter infrastructure. To the best of our knowledge this is the first work that proposes a scalable and generic approach for predicting these two service-level events.

A realistic testbed was deployed in a real datacenter consisting of a set of virtual machines competing for the resources of the physical machine in which they were running. Several experiment configurations were designed in order to generate normal, overload and noisy neighbor situations. Experiments were run for 1,000 hours generating a dataset of 260,000 records containing samples of the three variables collected at 10 seconds granularity. Labels for jitter and noisy neighbor use cases were added to each record for training and

testing deep learning models.

A large number of hyperparameter combinations were selected for each deep learning architecture and roughly 4,000 deep models were trained using them. 2,000 deep models were trained for predicting each service-level event (Noisy Neighbors and Jitter). The best models were selected using a validation dataset that follows the same statistical distribution than the training set. In order to show the generalization capabilities of these models when predicting in changing scenarios, they were tested against two different datasets that did not follow the same statistical distribution than the training set.

The obtained results show that accurate predictions can be obtained in both use cases when best deep models are used and a superior generalization ability is obtained with them when compared with traditional machine learning approaches such as Random Forests. These results suggest that deep models should be chosen in favour of Random Forest as they have shown a superior ability to interpolate and predict, even if inputs do not exactly follow the patterns of the data used for training.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the problem setting in detail. Deep learning architectures for modeling both use case predictors are presented in section III. Section IV depicts the experimental testbed, the scenarios and dataset variations jointly with the full set of experiments carried out and the analysis the obtained results. Finally, section V offers concluding remarks and outlines future work.

II. PROBLEM SETTING

We set up an experimental environment (Figure 1) in a real data center infrastructure for generating a dataset containing samples to be used as input to prediction models for two use cases: Noisy Neighbors and Jitter prediction. The environment consisted of a set of physical nodes, in which different VMs were instantiated. Several VMs were utilised for deploying a VoIP service with clients and servers, others introduced specific degrees of load and the rest acted as noisy neighbors, creating CPU load interferences on the same physical nodes.

Both use cases are deployed in the context of the same application, a VoIP client (grey VM in Figure 1) running in a VM located in a physical node and making a call to another client through a VoIP server (green VM) running in a VM placed in a second physical node. The call receiver is configured for playing music on-hold for the whole duration of the experiment. Along a variety of experiments, the VoIP client is dynamically exposed to changes in the behaviour of other VMs running in the same physical node. In particular, the VoIP call under testing compete for physical machine resources with other VoIP calls (orange VMs), while a set of additional applications (blue VMs) access concurrently to the same resources generating interferences. A noisy neighbor effect is defined as (one or more) VMs sharing resources with

FIGURE 1: Problem setting and experimental setup.

the application under test, thus affecting its performance. In our setting we focused on CPU noise, i.e. we provoke interferences to a VM in its access to CPU resources.

For each experiment, different patterns of CPU load and noise are configured in the VMs of the first node in order to affect the performance of the VoIP call under test. The first use case aims to predict whether noisy neighbors or overload situations are occurring at a specific instant of time along the VoIP call duration. Both types of events cause degradation in the performance of the VoIP VM and in particular they affect the listening quality of the VoIP call. The second use case tries to predict the observed jitter values of the VoIP call when load and noise interferences appear during the call. High values of jitter will eventually produce QoS degradation and so, a bad listening experience of the call.

During each experiment, samples of infrastructure variables are collected at a fixed granularity of 10 seconds and the resulting records are stored in a dataset and labeled with the corresponding events of each use case, so that a learning model can be trained to predict each of them. Aiming at providing scalable prediction models, each record of the collected dataset only contains samples of three infrastructure variables gathered from the physical machine that hosts the VM running the VoIP server. The three collected variables from the physical node are CPU usage, Inbound network traffic and Outbound network traffic. These three variables are the core input features to machine learning models although three additional feature extensions are proposed (subsection IV-D). The label for each record is added to the dataset at the same time samples are collected. A timestamp is also added to each record. Jitter values of the call under evaluation are measured in the listener client that is receiving the music on-hold and added directly to the corresponding sample in the dataset. Noisy neighbors labels (0=normal, 1= noisy, 2=overload) are derived from the load and noise configurations of each experiment at an instant of time and added to each dataset sample jointly with the jitter values. Grouping consecutive records of each experiment, the dataset is converted into a time series in order to be able to learn and

model the dynamics of the data along a time window.

It is worth noting that one of the key and distinguishing objectives of the first use case was not only to detect cpu interferences (noisy neighbor) but also to clearly differentiate them from an overload situation where not enough resources were assigned to a VM to begin with. The enforcement actions to be applied by an orchestrator when one of these events are detected in a real datacenter are totally different and therefore it is crucial to differentiate them with a high degree of confidence. In addition, the experimental scenarios are designed to reflect as much as possible the dynamic behaviour of cpu load and interferences in a real datacenter. Complementary, the ultimate goal of the second use case is to provide scalable jitter prediction mechanisms avoiding the deployment of additional applications in end-user equipment.

III. DEEP NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURES

Aiming to find the best performing prediction models we researched different architectural combinations of well-known artificial neural networks in order to take advantage of the specific characteristics of each of them. The proposed architectures were designed using as building blocks the following types of neural networks:

a: Fully Connected networks (FC).

These networks are a type of Feed Forward network that organises their nodes in layers with weighted connections feeding forward from one layer to next. Input vectors are propagated from the input layer through the hidden layers towards the output layer in order to map the input into output vectors. The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) [21], [22] is one of the most popular realizations of this type of network.

b: Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long short-term Memory (LSTM) networks.

RNNs simulate a discrete-time dynamical system for processing a sequence of values [15]. RNN architecture is similar to MLP but allows cyclical (recurrent) connections between neurons. These cyclical connections provide the

network with memory of the previous input sequences and therefore they allow to persist the network's internal state and hence to affect the network output [23]. A well-known RNN model is the Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM) [24] which is able to learn long-range dependencies in time series data. A typical LSTM architecture is represented by an input layer, several special hidden layers and one or more output layers. These special hidden layers consist of a set of recurrently connected subnets or memory blocks which allow to remember inputs for a long time. These layers maintain a state vector that implicitly contains information about the history of all the past elements of the processed sequence [26]. In addition, input layer processes one element at a time within an input sequence and output layers return the outputs of the hidden layers at different discrete time steps.

c: Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN).

These networks were initially introduced in [25] and are widely recognized by their ability for extracting the hierarchical features from data that have a known grid-like topology [15]. Input data can be represented as multiple arrays, dimensions and channels. In particular, 1-D arrays can represent regular time intervals in time-series data and have been applied to efficiently extract non-linear relationships that can appear among adjacent samples in a time-series. CNN architectures can build high-level features by composing low-level ones through a set of convolutional layers that discover the hierarchical relationships of the input data. A typical CNN architecture is represented by an input layer, several convolutional layers and one or more fully-connected layers at the end of the pipeline. Convolutional layers are comprised of three optional stages, namely convolution, detector and pooling. In the convolution stage, a convolution operation applies a filter (kernel) sliding it over the input data in order to produce feature maps. The detector passes feature maps through a non-linearity (e.g., a ReLU activation function) and finally, the pooling stage down-samples (e.g. averaging, getting the max or min) each feature map with a summary statistic of the nearby positions to produce a final feature map.

A. ARCHITECTURES

We designed and tested several neural network architectures to act as classifiers (Noisy neighbor use case) and regressors (Jitter prediction use case). These networks are composed of a combination of the following blocks: (a) Fully Connected layers, (b) 1-D Convolutional layers and (c) Long-Short Term Memory layers. We stacked combinations of these blocks to obtain the following architectures:

- FC network: it is composed of a single block of fully connected layers. The number of layers and units in each layer is configured by the random search process.
- CNN network: it consists of a convolutional block optionally followed by a block of fully connected layers. The convolutional block is composed of several 1-D convolutional layers applied in sequence. The number

of layers, filters and the size of each filter are configured during the random search process. A fixed stride of 1 and a zero-pad are pre-configured to preserve the dimensionality of the time window along all the convolutional layers. Since the dimensionality is relatively low, we do not employ subsampling so as to allow for depth. Each of these filters therefore produces a vector of length 11, each of whose elements undergoes a non-linear transformation. In addition, no pooling layers were employed as the dimensionality of the intermediate outputs were relatively small and did not require to be reduced.

- LSTM network: it comprises a LSTM block optionally followed by a block of fully connected layers. The LSTM block is made of several stacked LSTM layers using a input time window of 11 steps and different numbers of hidden units in each layer. The intermediate layers input the whole output sequence to next layer but only the last element of the last output sequence is passed to the FC block. The number of layers and intermediate units is configured by the random search process.
- Hybrid CNN_LSTM network: it is made of a sequence of two CNN and LSTM blocks optionally followed by a block of fully connected layers. The random search process determines the specific CNN, LSTM and FC network configurations.

A final layer is always added to the former networks in order to output the prediction – a single neuron with linear activation for regression or a set of neurons with softmax activation for classification–.

We want to find the micro and macro temporal non-linear relationships in the input variables, and to this end, we combine 1-D CNN and LSTM blocks. Using CNN with filters of size 3, 5 and 7 in time windows of 11 steps, we want to explore the potential relationships that could appear in adjacent input samples. Complementary, LSTM blocks will search for complex relations throughout the whole time window. Finally, FC blocks are utilised because of their agnostic treatment of input structure that will allow to search for non-linear relationships in the inputs without applying any special assumption about their structure. The combination of CNNs and LSTMs blocks has been previously explored in other fields ([29], [30]), but to the best of our knowledge there is no reference in the literature in the application of this type of networks to the use cases we present in this paper.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

We performed a set of experiments to evaluate the performance of the proposed model. Two use cases were considered: Noisy neighbors and Jitter prediction.

A. TESTBED

The experimental environment consists of five high performance physical servers with a proprietary management system running on an OpenStack cloud. Three physical servers are dedicated to orchestration and management and the rest

are compute machines. An open source voice-over-IP (VoIP) application (Asterisk) is deployed on one of the compute machines, in a single VM utilizing one core and 1024 MB of memory. In the second physical server a set of VMs are set up in order to create in a controlled way the noisy neighbor effect (i.e. CPU interference).

Firstly, an occurrence of SIPp (<http://sipp.sourceforge.net>), a traffic generator of VoIP calls, was deployed on a virtual machine and configured to initiate calls to a line in which the Asterisk server was playing music-on-hold. The noisy neighbor effect causes that the received music is played with audible distortion. A second VM is set up for deploying additional SIPp traffic generators in order to create a reasonable CPU load which can be configured from a set of discrete values [1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75, 100]. It must be noted that the last three values (50, 75 and 100) generate increasing overload situations and therefore, they are not utilised when a noise scenario is deployed. In order to introduce different levels of load, a number of competing SIPp clients are concurrently launched. For example, a load value of 15 launches 15 SIPp clients, each of them running in parallel 20 calls that are started at a rate of 2 calls per second and lasting 2,000 seconds each. Load can be increased dynamically in a periodic fashion under time intervals demand.

Finally, we deploy a third VM in which we run an application to generate noise on demand by repeatedly computing square roots of numbers in order to create interferences in the access to the CPU. This application was designed to mimic virtual network functions in behaviour but simple enough for experimentation and analysis. Therefore, this VM emulates the effect of noisy neighbors and allows us to differentiate this CPU interference from the normal load that SIPp calls generate. Similarly to load generation, noise can be configured in this third VM with two parameters (iterations and pause) that modulate the intensity and frequency of the CPU interferences. Noise can also be increased periodically in order to mimic more complex noise patterns. Different implementations were considered to examine the noisy neighbor effect on virtual machines. We experimented with both a single large VM occupying all physical CPUs and multiple small VMs, each occupying only one or two cores.

Input metrics (CPU load, inbound and outbound bandwidth) were obtained using Ceilometer, an OpenStack service being collected every 10 seconds, and aggregated into 30 second periods to avoid the impact of missing values or irregularities in the sampling frequency. Each of the resulting samples thus represents the average CPU load, inbound and outbound bandwidth of the monitored machine over 10 seconds. Labels are added automatically during sample collection. In the Noisy neighbor use case, we generate a multi class label consisting of 3 values: normal (label=0), noise (label=1) and load (label=2). Normal label is added to a sample when the music is heard without audible distortion as noise (cpu interference) is not introducing any significant disturbance. Conversely, when the music is played with distortion, a load label is added if the configured load level is greater than 40. A

noise label is added in the rest of the cases when music played with distortion since cpu interferences are severe enough to degrade the quality of the music. In the Jitter use case, the label is a float number obtained under request from an adhoc server deployed at the edges of the call connection that carries out the music-on-hold. Recall that, the added value of jitter prediction is precisely to avoid deploying any kind of adhoc meter for VoIP calls in a production environment.

B. EXPERIMENT SETUP

Three types of experiments were designed with the aim of testing how well machine and deep learning models can generalize and predict scenarios that are slightly different from the training one. The first experiment runs a fixed combination of load and noise by applying fixed values to the load and noise generators and not changing them during the whole experiment. The experiment starts running the VoIP call for receiving the music jointly with the noise and load applications, waits for 2 minutes to guarantee system warm up and stabilization, and after that CPU, BW-in and BW-out samples are collected every 10 seconds for 20 minutes. The noise application can be configured using a combination of pause and iterations values: 10, 100 or 1000 milliseconds for pause and 100, 1000, 3000, 6000 or 10,000 for the number of iterations. Load is configured at discrete steps of 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75 and 100. Normal and noise situations are set up by configuring the load generator with a load value less than 50 and the noise generator with a pair of pause and iterations values. Normal situation can also be generated by stopping the noise generator. Configuring a load value greater than 50 an overload situation is produced in the system. We ran this experiment 1450 times – on average 10 times for each configuration – picking uniformly at random load and noise configurations for each execution and obtaining a dataset with roughly 140,000 records after curation. This dataset is called *stationary*.

The second type of experiments models a dynamic scenario in which a fixed level of noise (cpu interference) is configured at start but a load level is increased gradually from 1 to 40 at regular time steps of 5 minutes. Firstly, the noise generator is launched and systems warms up. After that, load is iteratively increased 7 times every 5 minutes where CPU, BW-in and BW-out samples are collected with a granularity of 10 seconds, totalling 35 minutes for each experiment. This experiment represents a more realistic situation as the load level changes dynamically. As in the former experiment, labels are added automatically at the same time samples are gathered. We ran this experiment 451 times – on average 10 times for each configuration – picking uniformity at random noise configurations for each execution and obtaining a dataset with roughly 80,000 records after curation. This dataset is called *incremental*.

In the third type of experiments, we designed a dynamic scenario similar to the second (incremental load with non-changing noise levels) but using interpolated values for pause, iterations and load instead of the fixed ones that were

used in the second type of experiments. The aim of this type of experiment is to obtain a new dataset for testing the generalization ability of the machine learning models when trained with the stationary and incremental datasets that were generated using only fixed values for load and noise configurations. Therefore, instead of using fixed values in each experiment, we generate at random new values normally distributed for each noise and load configuration parameter. As in former experiments, labels are added automatically at the same time samples are collected. We ran this experiment 221 times – on average 5 times for each configuration – obtaining a dataset with roughly 42,000 records after curation. This dataset is called *incremental-random*.

After running all experiments approximately for 1,000 hours in the testbed, we obtained in total 260,000 records at 10 second granularity.

In order to exploit the temporal nature of the collected data, we concatenated consecutive samples in a time series of 11 steps (110 seconds). We conjecture that analyzing the input data over a sufficiently big time interval is likely to yield more information on the predicted event than using a sample from a single instant of time. Datacenter experts suggested us that events farther than 90 seconds from the current instant seem not to affect to predicted events. In fact, the trained Random Forests models revealed that feature importance vanished after 6-7 time steps (60-70 seconds) from the origin. Therefore, a larger window of 11 time steps was chosen in order to guarantee that deep learning models could exploit the temporal relationships of the input features. As showed in [1], this simple approach significantly boosts the performance of machine learning methods. Each input feature considered in the dataset is fed to the neural network in a separate channel. The resulting data set is thus an $N \times T \times D$ tensor, where N is the number of data points (the total number of records minus the number of concatenated readings), T is the length of the time window (i.e. the number of concatenated events) and D is the number of collected and extended features. The input to Random Forest models is a 1-D vector of $T \times D$ elements.

C. SCENARIOS

The normal way of preparing a set of deep models for the two use cases under consideration would consist of joining the available datasets (stationary, incremental and random-incremental) and split them in three sets training, validation and testing (70%, 15% and 15%, respectively). In a first stage, we followed this approach to obtain an estimation of each metric per use case and dataset. However, we aim to investigate the generalization capabilities of deep models that trained in a simplified scenario are deployed in a more complex one. To this end we designed two scenarios A and B. Scenario A investigates whether it is possible to train an accurate prediction model for dynamic scenarios (incremental and random-incremental datasets) using only for training samples obtained from experiments in which the initial state does not change along the whole experiment duration (stationary dataset). Therefore, after training each

model with the stationary dataset we test it against the incremental and random-incremental datasets. In Scenario B, we follow a less radical approach training deep models with the union of the stationary and incremental datasets that provide not only static but also dynamic situations, and keeping the random-incremental set for testing purposes. This scenario tries to demonstrate that even if the models are trained with experiments configured only with a set of fixed values for load and noise (stationary and incremental datasets), they are able to predict events in new scenarios that are generated with interpolated random values for load and noise (incremental-random dataset).

The objective of both scenarios is to show how well a deep model predicts a given situation when it has been trained with examples extracted from a simplified casuistry. Scenario A clearly proposes a more radical situation than B as the differences between the training and testing datasets are bigger in A than in B. A good performance in these scenarios would suggest that models trained only with fixed values for load and noise will behave nicely in similar production environments where load and noise values are not resulting from fixed patterns but from variables ones. Moreover, it would be interesting to demonstrate that deep models can approximate complex data distributions being trained only with small and limited subsets of such data distributions (i.e. the model is not presented with all the categories of data during training and yet it is able to interpolate and predict accurately events from the whole data distribution). This nice property, if present, would allow, during data collection, to save time and data center resources that tend to be scarce in production environments.

D. DATASET VARIATIONS

It is globally accepted that a general ML pipeline consists of three parts: feature engineering, model selection and algorithm selection. However, when deep learning is considered all these three steps are partly integrated and configured in the neural network architecture itself. Therefore, the problem to be solved frequently relays on searching the optimal neural architecture. Nevertheless, good core features and feature engineering still plays an important role in deep learning. In this context, it is a common practice to automatically derive features relying mainly on pre-defined transformations of the original features such as feature multiplications, square operations, discretization or normalization.

In this paper, feature derivation was applied to produce 4 variants of the core datasets in order to test whether feature extension can generate more compact network architectures or increase the accuracy of the final models. In addition to input normalization, we added logarithms, pair multiplications and squares of the original features, producing 4 variants of each training dataset:

- (v1) Original features: CPU, BW-in, BW-out,
- (v2) Logarithms: CPU, BW-in, BW-out, $\log(\text{CPU})$, $\log(\text{BW-in})$, $\log(\text{BW-out})$,

- (v3) Pair multiplications: CPU, BW-in, BW-out, CPU * BW-in, CPU * BW-out, BW-in * BW-out
- (v4) Squares: CPU, BW-in, BW-out, CPU², BW-in², BW-out²

We propose as novelty the logarithmic variation based on a previous experience of the authors modelling a regressor that approximates quotients of two linear combination of input values¹. We show in experimental sections IV-F and IV-G that this variation generate some advantages when training regressors (Jitter prediction) but we did not observe any significant enhancement in model performance when applied in the Noisy Neighbors classification use case.

E. MACHINE LEARNING SETUP

Noisy neighbor and Jitter prediction use cases were modelled as Multi-class Classification and Regression problems respectively. For each use case, we considered scenarios A and B for demonstrating the generalization abilities of machine learning models, and the four dataset variations (v1, v2, v3 and v4) for exploring whether feature extension could benefit model performance. In scenario A, the stationary dataset is used as the training set and the join of incremental and random-incremental datasets as the testing set. In scenario B, the combination of stationary and incremental datasets is utilised as the training set and the random-incremental as the testing set. For each use case, scenario and dataset variation, the following steps were repeated:

- 1) Perform a random search of the hyper parameter space by training a sufficient number of models and architectures.
- 2) Rank the best performing models after training using an appropriate metric on the validation set.
- 3) Test the best performing models using the corresponding testing dataset for each scenario and dataset variation.

All the models were trained using the Adam optimiser [20], minimising cross-entropy loss and squared errors for the multi-class classification and regression problems respectively. For training neural networks we set aside 10% of the training data for validation.

Model training consisted of a sequence of training iterations. Each training iteration comprises 5 epochs and at the end of each iteration accuracy or MAE (Mean Absolute Error) are computed on the validation set and used as early stopping criterion (i.e. after 10 iterations with no enhancement in the validation metric the training process stops). In any case, the training stops after 500 iterations. In addition to the former stopping conditions, we added a heuristic called the Median Stopping Rule as additional early stopping criterion. This heuristic rule implements the simple strategy of stopping a trial if its current performance during training

¹We extend the input with the logarithm of the input variables to allow approximating the logarithm of a quotient as the linear combination (subtraction) of two logarithms – this computation can be easily implemented by the output function of a single neuron –

TABLE 1: Hyperparameter table

Hyperparameter	Value
Minibatch size	[512,1024,2048]
Activation	Relu, LeakyRelu, Softplus, tanh
Dropout	[0, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 0.25, 0.5]
L2 regularization	[1e-5, 1e-3, 1e-2, 1e-1, 0.5, 1]
LeakyRelu alpha	[0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5]
Batch Normalization	[True, False]
NN Architecture	Hybrid, LSTM, CNN, FC
Range units FC	[5,300]
Range units LSTM	[10,250]
Max Layers LSTM	8
Max Layers CNN	5
Max Layers FC	8
CNN filter size	[1, 3, 5, 7]
CNN Num Filters	[16, 32, 64, 128, 256]

falls below the median of other previously finalized trials at similar steps of training. It is worth mentioning that this strategy does not depend on a parametric model and therefore does not introduce more hyperparameters. Golovin et al. [27] use this rule in their Vizier black-box optimization service at Google arguing that due to its generality this heuristic can be applied to a wide range of learning curves.

We perform a random search of the hyperparameter space for each machine learning model and choose the best performing models with the validation dataset. Random search process randomly selects different combinations of neural network architectures to be trained and tested. In particular, Fully connected, Convolutional networks, Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) networks and hybrid combinations of CNNs and LSTMs are randomly selected jointly with their corresponding hyper parameters. A detailed description of these neural network architectures was presented in section III. Table 1 summarises the set of hyper parameters used in the random search process jointly with the range of values utilised in our experiments. Using this random search process, we selected, trained and tested approximately 250 models per scenario, dataset variant and use case, roughly totalling 4,000 models. In order to accelerate training and testing processes we set up a tensorflow [45] framework running on a pool of 6 NVIDIA P100 (1), K80 (2) and 1080ti (3) GPUs.

In addition to deep models, we trained and tested several Random Forest models in order to compare the performance of deep models against a well known machine learning technique. Random forests [28] combine decision trees, bootstrap aggregation (bagging) and random feature selection and are widely popular because of their simplicity, efficiency and effectiveness. As it was showed in [2] other well known techniques such as Support Vector Machines did not attain the same performance as Random Forest, and therefore we

chose the latter as baseline for our experiments.

F. NOISY NEIGHBORS

This use case aims at predicting noisy neighbor CPU interferences and differentiating them from normal and overload situations. We model this use case as a multi-class classification problem where the expected output is a discrete set of values: normal, noise and overload. It is important to note that models should clearly differentiate noise from overload situations in order to be useful in realistic datacenter deployments. Combinations of scenarios A and B and dataset variations 1, 2, 3 and 4 were considered separately for training and testing different sets of deep models. Using a random search process we trained and tested approximately 2,000 deep models – 250 deep models per scenario and dataset variation –.

Models were ranked by accuracy on the validation and testing sets. It is worth noting that after running some preliminary trainings in which we used the macro f1-score metric on validation instead of accuracy for early stopping, we observed that the trained models with F1-score tend to consume much more training steps and to balance the number of false positive and negatives for each of the three categories (normal, noise and overload). In a real production environment the target values for false positives and negatives of each class do not have to be the same as the costs and penalties of incorrect actuations can be totally different depending on the involved classes. Furthermore, balancing these figures globally in the trained models could generate in a real deployment that a model trained with f1-score might be increasing the amount of false positives of class "0" – that enforces expensive actions to the system orchestrator – in benefit of reducing the number of false positives in class "1". In this context, data center engineers indicated us that the actions enforced when a noise false positive is produced in a normal situation (prediction of class "1" when we are in class "0") usually implies migrating without need at least one virtual machine to a different physical machine. Note that this action is significantly expensive in terms of datacenter resources (bandwidth, memory and cpu). Conversely, not detecting a sporadic noise problem (false negative of class "0") would not be so severe as the cpu interferences created among virtual machines might well disappear after a few seconds.

In addition, we chose accuracy as ranking metric in order to maximize the number of correct predictions and in particular the ones of the normal class. Considering that roughly 71% of the gathered examples were labelled as normal, maximising the model accuracy we were also increasing the number of correct predictions of the normal class, and consequently reducing the amount of the costly false positives of the noise class –at least the ones produced when the system is in the normal situation –. Nevertheless, in a realistic deployment, we suggest to investigate carefully the cost of the actions associated with the false positives and negatives of each category in order to design a custom metric that tries to reflect the actual cost of each type of incorrect prediction.

TABLE 2: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 1. Testing results. Best models on validation and on testing.

Models			
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 1+1+0 [(256,7)]+ [202]+[] 0.25, 1e-05, True Acc 0.995	#2 CNN 4+0 [(256,7),(16,1),(16,3),(256,5)]+[] 0.1, 1e-05, False Acc 0.992	#3 CNN_LSTM 1+4+2 [(32,5)]+ [240,161,53,20]+[83,8] 0.1, 1e-05, False Acc 0.990
Accuracy	(#125 test) 0.86946260	(#87 test) 0.89762899	(#114 test) 0.880044407
F1 (macro)	0.80038145	0.83249007	0.770576024
Prec (macro)	0.82369719	0.87026856	0.865073714
Recall (macro)	0.79819327	0.80995155	0.746346737
Confusion matrix	[87766 12128 230] [3561 22565 20] [828 47 1661]	[92184 7819 121] [4423 21715 8] [752 63 1721]	[88928 11157 39] [2887 23257 2] [1250 116 1170]
Random Forest			
	#52 FC 5 [286,227,161,69,20] 0, 0.01, False Acc 0.965	#46 FC 5 [127,113,80,6,6] 0.5, 1e-05, False Acc 0.967	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit
Accuracy	(#1 test) 0.94195922	(#2 test) 0.93588031	0.91043119
F1 (macro)	0.87240731	0.80121575	0.843478304
Prec (macro)	0.94299663	0.93417533	0.891548184
Recall (macro)	0.8217608	0.74003959	0.810993400
Confusion matrix	[98356 1704 64] [4866 21277 3] [708 131 1697]	[98147 1944 33] [4818 21324 4] [755 705 1076]	[94217 5818 89] [4805 21338 3] [624 198 1714]

For each scenario and dataset variation we present the results obtained by the best deep models on the testing set in tables 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9 and 10. For each model, we report accuracy, position in the testing list (ranked on testing accuracy), macro values for f1-score, precision and recall² and confusion matrix. Each table also includes the results obtained by a Random Forest model, which was used as baseline of traditional machine learning techniques, with 600 trees –no significant values were obtained beyond this value – gini index and no depth limit.

Each model is identified with a summary of its architectural details that are described using a compact notation (e.g. #1 CNN_LSTM 1+2+0 (256,7)]+[240,16]+[] 0.25, 1e-05, True, Acc 0.984). This nomenclature is composed of:

- 1) Model position in the validation ranking (#1)
- 2) Architecture type (CNN_LSTM)
- 3) List of three values describing the number of layers in CNN, LSTM and FC blocks respectively (1+2+0)
- 4) For each block, the number of units in each layer or the filter shape in the case of CNN blocks (CNN:[(256, 7)], LSTM: [240, 16], FC: [])
- 5) Dropout and L2 regularization values (0.25, 1e-05)
- 6) Batch-normalization (True)
- 7) Accuracy on the validation set (Acc 0.984).

Tables 2, 3, 4 and 5 show these results for the four dataset variations in scenario A and 7, 8, 9 and 10 for dataset variations in scenario B.

ROC and Precision-Recall curves for the two best models on validation for each scenario and data variation are shown in figures 2, 3, 4 and 5 for scenario A, and 6, 7, 8 and 9 for scenario B. In addition we report AUC (area under curve) of each curve in tables 6 and 11 for scenarios A and B respectively.

²In this problem Micro f1-score, precision and recall values are coincident with accuracy.

TABLE 3: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 2. Testing results. Best models on validation and on testing.

Models			
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 1+5+1 [(256,7)]+ [234,217,192,145,82]+[66] 0.1, 1e-05, True Acc 0.996	#2 CNN_LSTM 1+4+0 [(128,5)]+ [165,85,32,13]+[] 0.5, 1e-05, False Acc 0.992	#3 CNN_LSTM 4+4+0 [(64,5),(16,3),(32,3),(16,5)]+ [200,142,93,19]+[] 0.1, 1e-05, True Acc 0.990
Accuracy	(#135 test) 0.87634892	(#95 test) 0.89597534	(#80 test) 0.90509758
F1 (macro)	0.81253708	0.76361682	0.80895588
Prec (macro)	0.86265837	0.83494466	0.84852413
Recall (macro)	0.80003830	0.73228137	0.78235297
Confusion matrix	[87939 12144 41] [2795 23345 6] [884 57 1595]	[92455 7443 226] [4283 21841 22] [1402 23 1111]	[93732 6090 302] [4790 21342 14] [989 39 1508]
	#47 CNN_LSTM 3+4+0 [(64,3),(32,3),(32,5)]+ [185,166,66,28]+[] 0.25, 0.001, False Acc 0.956	#20 FC 4 [240,125,79,37] 0.5, 1e-05, False Acc 0.971	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit
Accuracy	(#1 test) 0.93884601	(#2 test) 0.93238669	0.909895501
F1 (macro)	0.86959790	0.81415055	0.843749946
Prec (macro)	0.93716389	0.91355609	0.891510593
Recall (macro)	0.82050307	0.75743604	0.811004865
Confusion matrix	[98098 1949 77] [5020 21122 4] [744 83 1709]	[97745 2250 129] [5026 21113 7] [1183 114 1239]	[94261 5774 89] [4929 21214 3] [632 179 1725]

TABLE 4: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 3. Testing results. Best models on validation and on testing.

Models			
Metrics on Testing	#1 LSTM 4+0 [207,174,74,42]+[] 0.01, 0.001, False Acc 0.984	#2 LSTM 5+0 [186,158,136,56,12]+[] 0, 0.001, False Acc 0.984	#3 LSTM 1+3 [91]+[75,12,5] 0.001, 0.001, True Acc 0.984
Accuracy	(#86 test) 0.90971693	(#80 test) 0.91104451	(#114 test) 0.90377777
F1 (macro)	0.82177180	0.826253934	0.83006583
Prec (macro)	0.90756190	0.887901254	0.86051574
Recall (macro)	0.76994229	0.783285066	0.80814783
Confusion matrix	[95439 4652 33] [5883 20263 0] [1023 38 1475]	[95577 4420 127] [5930 20191 25] [884 72 1580]	[93460 6438 226] [4891 21230 25] [758 56 1722]
	#39 LSTM 4+3 [213,103,72,71]+[67,56,29] 0.001, 0.001, True Acc 0.969	#46 CNN_LSTM 2+1+3 [(16,7),(64,1)]+ [124]+[93,55,13] 0.25, 0.01, False Acc 0.967	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit
Accuracy	(#1 test) 0.93490210	(#2 test) 0.93447510	0.910167228
F1 (macro)	0.86704022	0.85243203	0.846170732
Prec (macro)	0.93474445	0.92818083	0.890968755
Recall (macro)	0.81669825	0.80017510	0.8165019695
Confusion matrix	[98583 1456 85] [6045 20068 33] [737 29 1770]	[97919 2107 98] [5277 20863 6] [876 76 1584]	[93876 6163 85] [4521 21622 3] [611 188 1737]

Before running Scenario A and B experiments, we executed a set of random searches using the three available datasets (stationary, incremental and random-incremental) in order to obtain an estimation of accuracy and f1-score values that could be achieved with each dataset separately and with the combination of all of them. We applied a typical split of each dataset into 70/15/15 for training, validation and testing. The following range of accuracy and f1-score values were obtained on testing with the top 10 models for each dataset:

- Stationary:
Accuracy=[0.979, 0.991] and F1-score=[0.964, 0.983]
- Incremental:
Accuracy=[0.965, 0.984] and F1-score=[0.925, 0.968]
- Random-incremental:
Accuracy=[0.973, 0.982] and F1-score=[0.953, 0.974]
- The three datasets together:

TABLE 5: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 4. Testing results. Best models on validation and on testing.

Models			
Metrics on Testing	#1 LSTM 3+3 [231,100,59]+[93,69,62] 0, 0.001, False Acc 0.986	#2 LSTM 5+0 [163,161,79,63,53]+[] 0.01, 0.001, True Acc 0.986	#3 LSTM 1+3 [108]+[85,38,6] 0, 0.001, True Acc 0.984
Accuracy	(#29 test) 0.914165489	(#22 test) 0.91883142	(#60 test) 0.88984208
F1 (macro)	0.814218348	0.84573513	0.81315015
Prec (macro)	0.851228508	0.91155691	0.83673662
Recall (macro)	0.784399191	0.79982532	0.79840959
Confusion matrix	[95902 3898 324] [5761 20276 109] [823 141 1572]	[96237 3828 59] [5689 20450 7] [647 225 1664]	[91762 8061 301] [4986 21157 3] [680 158 1698]
	#32 FC 1 [137] 0.001, 1e-05, True Acc 0.956	#21 CNN_LSTM 3+1+3 [(64,1),(64,7),(64,1)]+ [170]+[85,71,50] 0.1, 0.001, False Acc 0.967	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit
Accuracy	(#1 test) 0.93307765	(#2 test) 0.93222365	0.910081828
F1 (macro)	0.86482551	0.86390964	0.843647017
Prec (macro)	0.91680079	0.91671734	0.891535503
Recall (macro)	0.82383993	0.82428920	0.810800284
Confusion matrix	[98225 1708 191] [5985 20134 27] [679 30 1827]	[96970 3036 118] [4780 21363 3] [559 234 1743]	[94290 5744 90] [4932 21211 3] [626 187 1723]

Accuracy=[0.970, 0.978] and F1-score=[0.948, 0.967].

As expected, these preliminary results suggest that predictions are easier and so, more precise, in static scenarios (stationary dataset) than in dynamic ones (incremental and random-incremental).

1) Scenario A

The results obtained in scenario A show that traditional and deep models both exhibit a decent prediction performance although worse than scenario B's. Tables 2, 3, 4 and 5 summarise these results for each dataset variant.

The best models ranked on validation accuracy are shown in the top half of each table and the models that performed the best on testing jointly with the Radom Forest model are reported in the down half. The best models ranked on validation accuracy attained on testing accuracy values in the range of [0.86,0.91] and F1-score ranged from 0.76 to 0.84. Random forest models obtained results in the same range (accuracy 0.91 and F1-score 0.84). Feature extension (i.e. dataset variations v2, v3 and v4) did not generate any significant advantage with respect to the original configuration of the three input variables (variation 1).

It is worth noting that having learnt nearly perfectly the training distribution (accuracy of 0.99 on validation), the performance of the best models on validation decreased on testing to the range of [0.86,0.91], reflecting the fact that the training and testing distributions are statistically less similar than their counterparts in scenario B. CNN_LSTM architectures are dominant on dataset variations 1 and 2 and LSTM configurations produce the best results on variations 3 and 4 which indicates that the temporal relationships of the input variables are eventually discovered more easily by LSTM blocks that are present in both architectures.

In addition, the best models ranked on testing accuracy produced slightly better values of accuracy ([0.86,0.93]) and

First Best model for Dataset variation 1 (CNN_LSTM 1+1+0)

Second best model for Dataset variation 1 (CNN 4+0)

First Best model for Dataset variation 3 (LSTM 4+0)

Second best model for Dataset variation 3 (LSTM 5+0)

FIGURE 2: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario A. Dataset variation 1.

FIGURE 4: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario A. Dataset variation 3.

First Best model for Dataset variation 2 (CNN_LSTM 1+5+1)

Second best model for Dataset variation 2 (CNN_LSTM 1+4+0)

First Best model for Dataset variation 4 (LSTM 3+3)

Second best model for Dataset variation 4 (LSTM 5+0)

FIGURE 3: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario A. Dataset variation 2.

FIGURE 5: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario A. Dataset variation 4.

F1-score ([0.80, 0.87]) occupying only middle positions in the validation ranking. As these models did not achieve to learn the distribution of the training data perfectly, they tend to make more general predictions than those models placed in high positions in the validation ranking. Therefore, some of these generic models perform better than well-fitted models when predicting events from a different data distribution.

It can be observed that with the exception of label 2 (overload class) the ROC and Precision-Recall curves (Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5) show a decent ability of the models for discriminating the true state of events – 95% of AUC values are above 0.9 (Table 6) –.

The main conclusion at the light of the results obtained in scenario A is that training deep models with a simplified data distribution (stationary dataset) will only produce a moderate prediction performance when models are deployed in scenarios where data patterns are different and more dynamic

(incremental and random-incremental datasets).

2) Scenario B

The results of Scenario B attain in general a better performance than Scenario A's. Tables 7, 8, 9 and 10 report a summary of the results on the testing set for each dataset variant. We firstly excluded from the analysis all the models with very small regularization values as they tend to overfit the training set and we want to obtain models able to generalise and predict unseen situations with a good accuracy.

The 5 best models ranked on validation accuracy are shown jointly with the Radom Forest model acting as baseline for traditional machine learning models. Note that as several of the best models on validation also occupy top positions in the testing ranking no best models on testing are shown as in scenario A. The reported models obtained accuracy in the range of [0.955,0.965] and F1-score values

TABLE 6: Noisy Neighbors prediction. Scenario *A*. AUC values for ROC and Precision-Recall curves. First and second best models on validation.

Dataset Variation	Models	
	#1 Validation	#2 Validation
Var 1	CNN_LSTM 1+1+0	CNN 4+0
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9306 AUC_P-R: 0.9770	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9396 AUC_P-R: 0.9803
	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9413 AUC_P-R: 0.8642	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9594 AUC_P-R: 0.9013
	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9308 AUC_P-R: 0.7572	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9309 AUC_P-R: 0.7559
	CNN_LSTM 1+5+1	CNN_LSTM 1+4+0
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9438 AUC_P-R: 0.9786	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9513 AUC_P-R: 0.9838
Var 2	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9531 AUC_P-R: 0.8821	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9578 AUC_P-R: 0.9033
	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9674 AUC_P-R: 0.7962	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9755 AUC_P-R: 0.7088
	LSTM 4+0	LSTM 5+0
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9316 AUC_P-R: 0.9697	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9434 AUC_P-R: 0.9794
	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9466 AUC_P-R: 0.8828	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9506 AUC_P-R: 0.8855
	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9574 AUC_P-R: 0.8005	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9285 AUC_P-R: 0.7109
Var 4	LSTM 3+3	LSTM 5+0
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9466 AUC_P-R: 0.9804	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9519 AUC_P-R: 0.9840
	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9482 AUC_P-R: 0.8842	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9535 AUC_P-R: 0.8928
	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9397 AUC_P-R: 0.6949	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9295 AUC_P-R: 0.7373

ranging from 0.923 to 0.944. It is worth noting that in this scenario Random Forest models obtained slightly worse figures but in the same range than deep models.

Feature extension (variations 2, 3 and 4) produced slightly better and consistent results, but deep models using only the original three input variables (variation 1) are able to extract by themselves nearly all non-linear dependencies contained in the input variables without the help of any feature extension. A great percentage of the best models on validation are also located in high positions in the testing ranking. This result indicates that models trained with the stationary and incremental datasets are able to predict with great accuracy

TABLE 7: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario *B*, Dataset variation 1. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Metrics on Testing	Models		
	#1 CNN_LSTM 1+1+1 [(128,3)]+ [154]+[39] 0.01, 0.001, True Acc 0.982	#2 CNN 2+0 [(128,1),(256,3)]+[] 0.1, 1e-05, False Acc 0.981	#3 CNN_LSTM 1+4+2 [(128,1)]+ [210,154,133,105]+[62,25] 0.01, 0.001, False Acc 0.976
Accuracy	(#20 test) 0.95503764	(#1 test) 0.96553125	(#18 test) 0.955850364
F1 (macro)	0.92332234	0.94289103	0.924311274
Prec (macro)	0.95316577	0.95983131	0.947453270
Recall (macro)	0.89886061	0.92734054	0.903946468
Confusion matrix	[31031 919 6] [850 8450 0] [106 0 473]	[31358 583 15] [776 8523 1] [67 0 512]	[31155 782 19] [952 8347 1] [93 0 486]
	#4 LSTM 5+0 [240,239,232,94,93]+[] 0.001, 0.001, True Acc 0.973	#5 CNN_LSTM 1+2+2 [(128,1)]+ [47,45]+[63,45] 0.1, 0.001, False Acc 0.973	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit-
Accuracy	(#7 test) 0.95585036	(#5 test) 0.96244771	0.96039201
F1 (macro)	0.924311274	0.93993283	0.930884518
Prec (macro)	0.947453270	0.96065465	0.959223202
Recall (macro)	0.955850364	0.92138355	0.906404948
Confusion matrix	[31155 782 19] [952 8347 1] [93 0 486]	[31283 664 9] [825 8475 0] [73 0 506]	[31305 641 10] [912 8388 0] [94 0 485]

TABLE 8: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario *B*, Dataset variation 2. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Metrics on Testing	Models		
	#1 CNN_LSTM 1+4+2 [(256,3)]+ [230,186,178,111]+[69,55] 0.5, 0.001, False Acc 0.976	#2 CNN 4+3 [(128,7),(64,1),(128,3),(64,3)]+ [99,56,17] 0.1, 0.001, True Acc 0.974	#3 CNN_LSTM 3+2+0 [(256,1),(64,7),(64,1)]+ [121,47]+[] 0.1, 0.01, True Acc 0.969
Accuracy	(#9 test) 0.9625433	(#5 test) 0.96383411	(#19 test) 0.9606310
F1 (macro)	0.9357937	0.93920645	0.9349213
Prec (macro)	0.9624636	0.95776323	0.9595875
Recall (macro)	0.9126666	0.96383411	0.9131146
Confusion matrix	[31313 636 7] [836 8464 0] [88 0 491]	[31226 717 13] [706 8594 0] [77 0 502]	[31310 636 10] [919 8381 0] [82 0 497]
	#4 CNN_LSTM 2+1+3 [(128,3),(32,1)]+ [74]+[80,63,30] 0.25, 0.01, True Acc 0.967	#5 CNN_LSTM 4+3+3 [(256,5),(128,3),(64,7),(16,7)]+ [195,33,28]+[29,15,13] 0.1, 0.001, True Acc 0.967	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit
Accuracy	(#10 test) 0.9618740	(#5 test) 0.9544639	0.9607505
F1 (macro)	0.9378924	0.9275337	0.932251513
Prec (macro)	0.9576899	0.9548429	0.9591610
Recall (macro)	0.9198050	0.9033207	0.90889251
Confusion matrix	[31375 565 16] [943 8356 1] [70 0 509]	[31374 568 14] [1242 8057 1] [80 0 499]	[31292 654 10] [887 8413 0] [91 0 488]

events generated in slightly different experiments not used during training (random-incremental dataset). In other words, having been trained with a specific data set, models are able to correctly interpolate predictions in unseen situations.

As in scenario A, CNN_LSTM architectures appear mostly among the best models (70%) followed by LSTM networks (20%) which suggests that (1) the macro temporal relationships of the input variables throughout the entire time window (11 steps) are easier to be found by LSMT blocks, and (2), the micro temporal relations that appear among adjacent samples can be discovered by 1-D CNN blocks using filters of sizes ranging from 3 to 7 time steps.

Confusion matrices exhibit a significant decrease in the number of false positives and negatives when compared with scenario A's. In particular, the costly noise false positives

TABLE 9: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario B, Dataset variation 3. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models				
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 4+4+0 [(64,7),(16,3),(32,7),(64,5)]+ [234,193,44,24]+[1] 0.01, 0.001, False Acc 0.975	#2 LSTM 5+3 [236,185,182,163,125]+[95,90,5] 0.01, 0.001, False Acc 0.974	#3 CNN_LSTM 4+2+1 [(16,3),(256,3),(128,3),(32,5)]+ [246,100]+[74] 0.001, 0.001, False Acc 0.973	
Accuracy	(#1 test) 0.96266284	(#33 test) 0.95730847	(#6 test) 0.96359507	
F1 (macro)	0.940350059	0.92822584	0.94279927	
Prec (macro)	0.958706560	0.94663281	0.96088910	
Recall (macro)	0.923853136	0.91345129	0.92692813	
Confusion matrix	[31241 704 11] [776 8524 0] [71 0 508]	[30867 1075 14] [604 8696 0] [93 0 486]	[31175 775 6] [671 8629 0] [71 0 508]	
	#4 LSTM 1+0 [113]+[1] 0, 0.01, False Acc 0.972	#5 LSTM 4+0 [198,198,85,57]+[1] 0.001, 0.001, True Acc 0.972	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit-	
Accuracy	(#11 test) 0.96237600	(#41 test) 0.95494203	0.96063105	
F1 (macro)	0.93687345	0.93219994	0.93277265	
Prec (macro)	0.95643384	0.94790403	0.95905391	
Recall (macro)	0.91977777	0.92024378	0.90986926	
Confusion matrix	[31172 772 12] [709 8591 0] [81 0 498]	[30715 1235 6] [563 8737 0] [81 0 498]	[31289 657 10] [891 8409 0] [89 0 490]	

TABLE 10: Noisy Neighbour prediction. Scenario B, Dataset variation 4. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models				
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 4+5+3 [(32,3),(32,3),(16,1),(256,3)]+ [213,183,59,50,12]+[83,69,35] 0.25, 1e-05, False Acc 0.984	#2 CNN_LSTM 2+4+1 [(32,1),(256,3)]+ [229,125,109,17]+[68] 0, 0.001, True Acc 0.982	#3 CNN_LSTM 3+1+0 [(128,3),(32,1),(32,5)]+ [233]+[1] 0.25, 1e-05, False Acc 0.981	
Accuracy	(#10 test) 0.96297358	(#34 test) 0.95702163	(#5 test) 0.96443169	
F1 (macro)	0.94045724	0.92703835	0.94282081	
Prec (macro)	0.95617201	0.95353201	0.95844948	
Recall (macro)	0.92721647	0.90495386	0.92856949	
Confusion matrix	[31042 906 8] [559 8740 1] [75 0 504]	[31057 891 8] [800 8500 0] [99 0 480]	[31266 677 13] [731 8568 1] [66 0 513]	
	#4 CNN_LSTM 2+2+2 [(256,1),(128,7)]+ [129,117]+[86,9] 0.25, 1e-05, True Acc 0.980	#5 CNN_LSTM 2+5+0 [(16,7),(256,1)]+ [219,137,65,35,26]+[1] 0.01, 0.001, True Acc 0.979	Random Forest 600 trees, no depth limit-	
Accuracy	(#20 test) 0.96022469	(#29 test) 0.9583602	0.96185012	
F1 (macro)	0.93465814	0.9277212	0.93374294	
Prec (macro)	0.95906549	0.9538777	0.95916658	
Recall (macro)	0.91273926	0.9055442	0.91157016	
Confusion matrix	[31492 446 18] [1127 8173 0] [73 0 506]	[31134 811 11] [822 8478 0] [98 0 481]	[31294 651 11] [845 8455 0] [88 1 490]	

of the normal class have decreased from several thousands to a few hundreds in all the reported models. Additionally, the separation between noise and overload classes is nearly perfect: 66% of the reported models generated no false positives and negatives for these two classes, and in the rest of the models the total amount was only 1. Additionally, ROC and Precision-Recall curves for scenario B (Figures 6, 7, 8 and 9) show a significantly better ability of the models for discriminating the true state of events – no AUC value is below 0.92 and 66% are above 0.98 (Table 11)–.

At the light of these results we conclude that it is possible to predict noisy neighbor interferences with accuracy and differentiate them from overload situations with a moderate rate of false positives and negatives. In addition, the dynamic behaviour (incremental dataset) that is present in the training set of scenario B allows to obtain models that can interpolate

First best model on validation for Dataset variation 1 (CNN_LSTM 1+1+1)

Second best model on validation for Dataset variation 1 (CNN 2+0)

FIGURE 6: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario B. Dataset variation 1.

First Best model on validation for Dataset variation 2 (CNN_LSTM 1+4+2)

Second best model on validation for Dataset variation 2 (CNN 4+3)

FIGURE 7: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario B. Dataset variation 1.

and predict with a significantly better performance than scenario A's. Best deep models obtain slightly better results than Random Forest's in both scenarios, and tend to generalise more effectively when the data distribution on testing is rather different from the training one (scenario A). This result encourages to select deep models against Random Forest for realistic deployments as they have shown a superior ability to interpolate and predict when inputs do not exactly follow the patterns of the data used for training. Moreover, when GPUs are available for real-time deployments, the prediction speed of deep models using a modest GPU (Nvidia Geforce 1080 ti) is in the range of dozens of microseconds while Random Forest models spend hundreds of microseconds per prediction when run in the same off-the-shelf PC workstation.

First best model on validation for Dataset variation 3 (CNN_LSTM 4+4+0)

Second best model on validation for Dataset variation 3 (LSTM 5+3)

FIGURE 8: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario B. Dataset variation 3.

First Best model on validation for Dataset variation 4 (CNN_LSTM 4+5+3)

Second best model on validation for Dataset variation 4 (CNN_LSTM 2+4+1)

FIGURE 9: Testing ROC and Precision-Recall curves. Scenario B. Dataset variation 4.

G. JITTER PREDICTION

The second use case aims to predict the jitter values observed in a VoIP connection using as input the same three variables utilised in the Noisy Neighbors use case. We model this use case as a regression problem where the output is a float number representing the expected jitter value of the call at an instant of time.

Firstly, we ran a set of random searches using the available datasets (stationary, incremental and random-incremental) in order to obtain an estimation of the maximum accuracy (MAE values on testing) that could be achieved with each dataset separately and with the combination of all of them. We applied a typical split of each dataset into 70/15/15 for training, validation and testing. The following range of MAE values were obtained on testing with the top 10 deep models for each dataset: (a) stationary [8.8, 9.6], (b)

TABLE 11: Noisy Neighbors prediction. Scenario B. AUC values for ROC and Precision-Recall curves. First and second best models on validation.

Dataset Variation	Models	
	#1 Validation	#2 Validation
Var 1	CNN_LSTM 1+1+1	CNN 2+0
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9869 AUC_P-R: 0.9956	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9922 AUC_P-R: 0.9974
	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9882 AUC_P-R: 0.9669	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9930 AUC_P-R: 0.9796
Var 2	CNN_LSTM 1+4+2	CNN 4+3
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9902 AUC_P-R: 0.9969	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9927 AUC_P-R: 0.9977
	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9916 AUC_P-R: 0.9751	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9937 AUC_P-R: 0.9789
Var 3	CNN_LSTM 4+4+0	LSTM 5+3
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9906 AUC_P-R: 0.9971	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9884 AUC_P-R: 0.9962
	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9914 AUC_P-R: 0.9688	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9901 AUC_P-R: 0.9736
Var 4	CNN_LSTM 4+5+3	CNN_LSTM 2+4+1
	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9904 AUC_P-R: 0.9969	label:0 AUC_ROC: 0.9802 AUC_P-R: 0.9898
	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9916 AUC_P-R: 0.9760	label:1 AUC_ROC: 0.9834 AUC_P-R: 0.9649
Var 4	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9983 AUC_P-R: 0.9716	label:2 AUC_ROC: 0.9771 AUC_P-R: 0.9209

incremental [6.2, 6.9], (c) random-incremental [5.7, 6.0] and (d) all three datasets together [7.6, 8.0]. At the light of these preliminary results it can be observed that jitter prediction is not as easy to predict when load and noise are constant (stationary dataset) as when load is increasing (incremental and random-incremental datasets). This result goes in the opposite direction of which we obtained in the Noisy Neighbors use case in which predictions were more accurate in the stationary dataset. We conjecture that jitter is jointly affected by increasing cpu loads plus external factors not present in the three input variables. Therefore, predictions made with the stationary dataset are less accurate because neither there is a load increase in this dataset nor external factors are known. When incremental and incremental-random datasets

TABLE 12: Jitter prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 1. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models					
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 3+2+0 [(256,1),(16,3),(64,7)]+ [143,58]+ 0.01, 0.1, False Validation MAE 8.416	#2 CNN_LSTM 1+1+2 [(64,3)]+ [218]+[32,14] 0.1, 0.1, False Validation MAE 8.714	#3 CNN_LSTM 4+5+0 [(128,7),(256,1),(128,7),(64,1)]+ [197,129,112,86,36]+ 0.1, 0.001, True Validation MAE 8.734		
	R2	0.4703010	0.5315273	0.4039419	
MSE	796.7406145	704.6477608	896.553898		
MAE	12.98681 (#145 test)	10.0843507 (#71 test)	11.0562171 (#108 test)		
	#4 CNN_LSTM 2+4+0 [(32,3),(128,1)]+ [212,123,54,48]+ 0.25, 0.001, True Validation MAE 8.756	#5 CNN_LSTM 1+1+0 [(64,5)]+ [111]+ 0.01, 0.5, True Validation MAE 8.763	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)		
R2	0.6477451	0.6389002	0.47698685		
MSE	529.8400769	543.144061	786.6842921		
MAE	8.4387923 (#6 test)	8.9485994 (#16 test)	13.9581968		

are used, at least one of the two affecting factors is present (load increase) and therefore, obtained predictions are more accurate producing smaller MAE values.

After these preliminary experiments, and as in the former use case, a random search for each scenario and dataset variation was ran using the hyper parameter space described in table 1. We trained roughly 250 models for each scenario and variation, totalling more than 2,000 trained deep models. Tables 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19 present a summary of the obtained results. Each table shows the testing results for the 5 best trained models ranked by MAE on the validation dataset. Additionally a Random Forest model was trained and used as baseline for comparison with deep models.

It is worth noting that traditional time-series models such as ARIMA based methods (e.g Box-Jenkins) were not considered in these experiments as it has been showed in [31] that deep models, and in particular convolutional networks, obtain a superior prediction performance in regression problems when inputs are modelled as time series.

For each model, a compact nomenclature of their architecture is provided jointly with the MAE computed on the validation dataset. This nomenclature, previously described in IV-F, is composed of (1) the name of the architecture, (2) a list of three values describing the number of layers in CNN, LSTM and Fully Connected blocks respectively, (3) the number of units in each layer for each block, or the filter shape in the case of CNN blocks, (4) the dropout and L2 regularization values applied during training and (5) whether batch-normalization was applied or not (True/False). The resultant R2 (coefficient of determination), MAE (Mean Absolute Error) and MSE (Mean Squared Error) values obtained on the testing dataset are shown below the model description. The position of the model in the testing list (ranked by MAE) is also provided (in parenthesis) to give an insight of the generalization capabilities of the model in comparison with the rest of the trained models.

1) Scenario A

The obtained results in scenario A (tables 12, 13, 14 and 15) reflect that predictions are not as good as in scenario B because of the significant differences between the train-

TABLE 13: Jitter prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 2. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models					
Metrics on Testing	#1 LSTM 3+0 [191,183,58]+ 0, 0.001, True Validation MAE 8.589	#2 CNN_LSTM 3+7+0 [(256,3),(16,1),(64,3)]+ [209,160,143,88,58,22,21]+ 0.01, 0.001, False Validation MAE 8.665	#3 CNN_LSTM 3+1+0 [(16,1),(256,7),(64,7)]+ [107]+ 0.01, 0.01, False Validation MAE 8.803		
	R2	0.5768718	0.4144979	0.5763835	
MSE	637.783040	882.5300542	638.51903610		
MAE	9.379374 (#63 test)	11.017149 (#127 test)	9.8001049 (#83 test)		
	#4 LSTM 4+0 [228,206,199,124]+ 0.01, 0.1, False Validation MAE 8.842	#5 LSTM 4+1 [239,144,49,25]+[46] 0.001, 0.1, False Validation MAE 8.860	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)		
R2	0.632643068	0.54437974	0.47883953		
MSE	566.0858194	686.7585504	783.897603		
MAE	8.4363044 (#7 test)	9.47819316 (#66 test)	13.95993682		

TABLE 14: Jitter prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 3. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models					
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 2+5+0 [(256,7),(256,1)]+ [206,144,136,55,32]+ 0.5, 0.001, True Validation MAE 8.250	#2 LSTM 2+0 [134,130]+ 0, 0.01, True Validation MAE 8.546	#3 FC 6 [214,209,171,167,128,14] 0.1, 0.001, False Validation MAE 8.574		
	R2	0.47493559	0.53735372	0.5303456	
MSE	789.76967613	695.8841582	706.4252495		
MAE	11.363973 (#70 test)	11.1898790 (#66 test)	11.590823 (#77 test)		
	#4 CNN_LSTM 2+4+0 [(64,5),(256,3)]+ [212,114,87,22]+ 0.25, 1e-05, False Validation MAE 8.667	#5 CNN_LSTM 1+2+1 [(16,5)]+ [143,93]+[17] 0.01, 0.1, False Validation MAE 8.710	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)		
R2	0.73898980	0.5129621	0.4917298		
MSE	692.187471	732.5724133	764.50880641		
MAE	9.680145 (#15 test)	11.9904853 (#89 test)	13.93427164		

TABLE 15: Jitter prediction. Scenario A, Dataset variation 4. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models					
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 1+6+0 [(16,7)]+ [239,229,210,131,47,12]+ 0.1, 0.001, False Validation MAE 8.630	#2 CNN_LSTM 1+7+0 [(64,5)]+ [211,68,54,45,33,20,19]+ 0.01, 0.001, False Validation MAE 8.727	#3 CNN_LSTM 1+3+1 [(128,3)]+ [238,78,61]+[53] 0.25, 0.1, False Validation MAE 8.748		
	R2	0.5621877	0.20159179	0.6690082	
MSE	658.530388	1200.916659	497.8574721		
MAE	11.170722 (#22 test)	15.15627 (#44 test)	8.2844890 (#1 test)		
	#4 CNN_LSTM 1+2+0 [(128,5)]+ [173,47]+ 0.1, 0.5, False Validation MAE 8.766	#5 CNN_LSTM 2+2+0 [(256,1),(128,3)]+ [232,228]+ 0.01, 0.5, False Validation MAE 8.847	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)		
R2	0.5560878	0.3111990	0.474177821		
MSE	667.70544317	1036.0521731	790.909469618		
MAE	10.161937 (#13 test)	15.2067168 (#45 test)	14.223547198		

TABLE 16: Jitter prediction. Scenario C, Dataset variation 1. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models				
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 3+3+0 [(256,5),(256,3),(64,7)]+ [56,42,14]+ 0.1, 0.01, False Val MAE 7.200	#2 CNN_LSTM 2+3+0 [(32,1),(64,5)]+ [138,118,85]+ 0.001, 0.01, False Val MAE 7.522	#3 CNN_LSTM 1+6+0 [(32,1)]+ [122,119,108,100,60,30]+ 0, 1e-05, False Val MAE 7.535	
	R2	0.70543	0.74379	0.60360
MSE	485.94253	422.65316	592.62346	
MAE	6.27083 (#1 test)	6.29166 (#2 test)	8.8805 (#18 test)	
	#4 CNN_LSTM 2+7+0 [(64,3),(32,7)]+ [125,110,93,66,27,18,15]+ 0.1, 0.001, True Val MAE 7.557	#5 CNN_LSTM 3+3+0 [(64,7),(256,1),(128,7)]+ [122,115,32]+ 0.01, 1e-05, True Val MAE 7.584	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)	
R2	0.60243	0.58806	0.77180	
MSE	594.36275	615.85036	365.73745	
MAE	9.50703 (#19 test)	10.42110 (#14 test)	6.13532	

TABLE 17: Jitter prediction. Scenario *C*, Dataset variation 2. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models				
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 2+5+0 [(16,1),(64,5)]+ [146,134,130,51,35]+[] 0.01, 0.01, True Val MAE 7.332	#2 CNN_LSTM 2+2+0 [(16,1),(128,3)]+ [130,122]+[] 0.01, 0.001, True Val MAE 7.452	#3 LSTM 4+0 [67,53,28,17]+[] 0.01, 0.001, True Val MAE 7.473	
R2	0.72193486	0.7306727	0.7012186	
MSE	444.845980	430.867123	493.6114567	
MAE	6.16419299 (#8 test)	6.201474 (#12 test)	6.4130957 (#32 test)	
Metrics on Testing	#4 CNN_LSTM 1+5+0 [(32,5)]+ [149,139,111,86,10]+[] 0.01, 0.01, False Val MAE 7.528	#5 CNN_LSTM 2+2+0 [(128,5),(64,1)]+ [120,71]+[] 0.001, 0.01, False Val MAE 7.565	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)	
R2	0.68845579	0.7186903	0.769504	
MSE	498.40548861	450.0365349	369.41255	
MAE	6.112075 (#4 test)	5.89964664 (#1 test)	6.13388	

TABLE 18: Jitter prediction. Scenario *C*, Dataset variation 3. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models				
Metrics on Testing	#1 CNN_LSTM 2+3+0 [(64,7),(256,5)]+ [240,218,171]+[] 0.01, 0.01, False Validation MAE 7.899	#2 CNN_LSTM 2+2+0 [(256,3),(128,1)]+ [71,62]+[] 0.01, 1e-05, False Validation MAE 7.992	#3 CNN_LSTM 1+3+0 [(16,7)]+ [89,88,61]+[] 0.1, 0.1, False Validation MAE 8.006	
R2	0.7175727	0.75346505	0.75218541	
MSE	443.58642345	388.415091952	397.1791876	
MAE	6.2834117 (#1 test)	6.44864556 (#2 test)	7.1170347 (#22 test)	
Metrics on Testing	#4 LSTM 2+0 [169,150]+[] 0.01, 0.1, True Validation MAE 8.034	#5 CNN_LSTM 1+8+2 [(256,1)]+ [204,175,114,101,48,20,13,12]+ [91,80] 0, 1e-05, False Validation MAE 8.036	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)	
R2	0.73898980	0.7235929	0.7731435	
MSE	418.328149	435.4785703	363.5890580	
MAE	7.1616689 (#25 test)	6.5803383 (#4 test)	6.1497260	

ing (stationary) and the testing (incremental plus random-incremental) datasets. It is worth to note that dataset variation 2 (logarithms) seems to be more stable on testing than the other three variations. Variation 2 obtains MAE values on testing in a narrow range of values ([8.4,9.8] in four of five models) whereas the other variations fluctuate in a wide range of values (variation 1: [8.4,12.9], variation 3: [9.6,11.9] and variation 4: [8.1,15.1]). These results suggest that variation 2 features could be chosen in order to obtain more stable results when the model is going to be deployed in realistic scenarios where data patterns are different from the ones utilised for training. The top 5 models on validation in each dataset

TABLE 19: Jitter prediction. Scenario *C*, Dataset variation 4. Testing results. 5 Best models on validation.

Models				
Metrics on Testing	#1 LSTM 8+0 [219,195,144,114,77,71,64,47]+[] 0.01, 0.001, True Val MAE 7.511	#2 LSTM 3+0 [101,57,18]+[] 0, 0.01, False Val MAE 7.515	#3 LSTM 5+1 [156,133,130,72,51]+[70] 0.01, 1e-05, False Val MAE 7.632	
R2	0.737338505	0.697036	0.693822	
MSE	409.9272207	472.82481324	477.84088	
MAE	6.371098521 (2# test)	6.401247 (#3 test)	6.738607 (#14 test)	
Metrics on Testing	#4 CNN_LSTM 2+6+0 [(256,7),(16,1)]+ [231,214,186,155,141,100]+[] 0.1, 0.001, False Val MAE 7.733	#5 CNN_LSTM 1+1+0 [(32,5)]+ [44]+[] 0.1, 0.1, False Val MAE 7.779	Random Forest (600 trees, no depth limit)	
R2	0.750240	0.7766861	0.7700582	
MSE	384.7503555	344.011655	368.533858	
MAE	6.7926527 (18# test)	6.6235321 (10# test)	6.141517	

variation are ranked in a wide range of positions on the testing list, and therefore, choosing the best trained models ranked by validation error does not guarantee the best prediction results on a realistic deployment where data patterns are not coincident with the ones contained in the training dataset. We observed in some cases that moderate degrees of dropout regularization tend to decrease this erratic behaviour but this is a question that still needs to be researched more in depth in the future. Hybrid CNN_LSTM architectures are dominant when trained models are ranked by validation error: 75% of the top 5 models are hybrid CNN_LSTM followed by a 20% of LSTM. These architectures, and in particular LSTM blocks, show a clear advantage for predicting jitter values when complex temporal relations are present in the data. When testing results are analysed, no specific architecture seems to perform better than the others mainly due to the big differences between training and testing datasets. Random Forest models obtained similar worse results on the four dataset variations (Validation MAE in the range of [13.9,14.2]).

2) Scenario B

The attained accuracy of testing results in scenario B is significantly better than the one obtained in scenario A. Two factors are mainly responsible for this improvement. Firstly, training and testing distributions are more similar in scenario B than in A. Secondly, we observed in preliminary experiments that predicting jitter in scenarios where cpu load increases, produced results with much better accuracy. The best models of dataset variations 2, 3 and 4 obtained MAE values in the range of [5.9,7.1] although variation 1 models exhibited a less consistent performance with values laying in a wider range [6.2,10.2]. As it happened in Scenario A, the best models of variation 2 (logarithm) achieve better results than the rest and in a narrower range [5.9,6.4]. Regarding that the statistical distributions of records in the training and testing datasets in scenario B are closer than in scenario A, the best models on validation are also ranked in the top positions in the testing phase. These results encourage to deploy models previously trained with a statistical simplification of the real data (stationary and incremental datasets) in realistic environments (random-incremental dataset) – the resultant models can moderately interpolate predictions in situations not considered during the training phase-. Similarly to scenario A, hybrid CNN_LSTM architectures are predominant among the best models ranked by MAE on validation in every dataset variation –15 of 20 models are hybrid CNN_LSTM models and the rest are LSTM architectures-. It is worth noting that Random Forest models achieved similar values for accuracy metrics on testing than the best deep models. Additionally, Random Forest feature importance results revealed that time windows of 6-7 steps (60-70 seconds) contain the most important features for predicting jitter with accuracy. Therefore, jitter behaviour seems to be mainly related to the changes appeared in the system during the last minute. This experimental result was coincident with the suggestions

provided previously by datacenter engineers. Nevertheless, we applied a more conservative approach and grouped data samples in larger windows of 11 time steps (110 seconds) as complex non-linear relationships might be present in greater periods of times.

At the light of these results we can summarise that deep models have always obtained the best accuracy values on testing even if the statistical distribution of the training and testing datasets were different (Scenarios A and B). Conversely, Random Forest models have only performed well when both datasets were similar (Scenario B). The superior complexity of deep models allows to extract intricate non-linear relationships contained in the input variables jointly with the inherent temporal relations that are present in consecutive samples. Therefore, these results suggest the convenience of choosing deep models instead of Random Forest in production environments in order to endow predictors with a greater generalization capability when changes in the data patterns are expected to appear sooner or later.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a scalable and generic method based on deep neural networks for predicting service level events in a datacenter infrastructure taking as input only a reduced number of statistics (CPU usage, Inbound network traffic and Outbound network traffic) that are sampled at the physical machines and are independent from the service-level events we want to predict. Additionally, the reduced dimensionality of the input is also beneficial for the real-time operation of the models as their computation time is directly affected by the input size.

Two service level events were considered and modelled in different use cases. Firstly, we proposed the prediction of the so-called Noisy Neighbors effect with deep learning models. This situation appears when virtual machines that are running in the same physical machine compete for physical machine resources creating interferences among them and producing a performance degradation in the system. We set up a realistic testbed on a real datacenter and run experiments aiming not only to detect noisy CPU interferences but also to clearly differentiate them from overload situations as each of them implies different corrective actions in datacenters. Secondly, and using the same testbed and input variables, we proposed deep learning models for predicting the jitter values of one of the VoIP calls deployed in the testbed experiments. To the best of our knowledge this is the first work that proposes a scalable and generic approach for predicting these two types of service-level events that are so different.

The testbed consisted of a set of virtual machines running applications that created VoIP calls competing for the resources of the physical machine in which they were running. A variety of experiments were conducted in order to dynamically generate different combinations of normal, overload and noisy neighbors situations in the physical machines. These experiments were run for 1,000 hours generating a labelled dataset of 260,000 records containing samples of the three variables collected at a 10 seconds granularity.

Two scenarios A and B were designed to research the generalization capabilities of deep models that after having been trained in a simplified scenario are deployed in a more complex one. As the differences between training and testing sets in scenario A were larger than in B, in both use cases, we obtained better performance in scenario B than in A when testing deep models. Random Forest, as a representative of traditional machine learning methods, performed similarly to deep models only in scenario B, which suggests to select deep models for realistic deployments as they have shown a superior ability to generalise predictions when inputs do not exactly follow the statistical patterns of the data used for training (scenario A).

Three feature extensions were automatically derived and added to the original input variables relying on pre-defined transformations of the original features (product, square and logarithms). Some performance increase was obtained when training regressors (Jitter prediction use case) but we did not observe any significant enhancement when applied in the Noisy Neighbors use case.

A set of different deep learning architectures was proposed and roughly 4,000 deep models were trained and tested for predicting each of the two service level events. Noisy Neighbors results show that it is possible to predict these interferences with accuracy and differentiate them from overload situations with a moderate rate of false positives and negatives. The best deep models obtained slightly better results than Random Forest's in both scenarios, the former performing better than the later when the data distribution on testing was different from the training one, which is a clear sign of better model generalization. Similarly, in the Jitter prediction use case, deep models obtained the best MAE values on testing even if the statistical distribution of the training and testing datasets were different.

These results encourage us to select deep models against Random Forest for realistic deployments as they have shown a superior ability to interpolate and predict, even if inputs do not exactly follow the patterns of the data used for training. In addition, when GPUs are available, prediction speed of deep models is approximately one order of magnitude faster – in the range of dozens of microseconds using a NVidia Geforce 1080ti – when compared with Random Forest's in the same off-the-shelf PC workstation.

A natural extension of this work is to research the actuation part of the Noisy Neighbor predictor as it is a complex problem involving many different variables and objective functions. Firstly, when a noisy neighbor situation is detected, the system has to identify the VMs that are causing the problem. After detecting this event, it is required to take a decision on which VMs and where they should be moved. It is worth noting that this actuation process is extremely costly as implies the transmission and copy of several gigabytes from one physical machine to another, and therefore, a careful and conservative real-time analysis should be done in order to avoid costly actuations when false positives of noisy neighbors are predicted. Another research line can

address more complex scenarios where the interferences do not come exclusively from CPU consumers but also from network usage patterns.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to these results received funding from the European Union under the H2020 grant agreement 671625 (project CogNet).

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Ordozgoiti, A. Mozo, S. Gómez-Canaval, U. Margolin, E. Rosensweig, I. Segall. "Deep convolutional neural networks for detecting noisy neighbours in cloud infrastructure". In Proceedings of European Symposium on Artificial Neural Networks, Computational Intelligence and Machine Learning - ESSAN, pp. 571–579, 2017.
- [2] U. Margolin, A. Mozo, B. Ordozgoiti, D. Raz, E. Rosensweig, and I. Segall. "Using machine learning to detect noisy neighbors in 5G networks", arXiv preprint arXiv:1610.07419, 2016.
- [3] T. Lorido-Botran, S. Huerta, L. Tomás, J. Tordsson, B. Sanz, "An unsupervised approach to online noisy-neighbor detection in cloud datacenters". *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 89, pp. 188–204, 2017.
- [4] Ramadan, H. H., and Kashyap, D. "Quality of Service (QoS) in Cloud Computing", *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, 8(3), 318-320, 2017.
- [5] P. Rad and R. V. Boppana and P. Lama and G. Berman and M. Jamshidi, "Low-latency software defined network for high performance clouds", 2015 10th System of Systems Engineering Conference (SoSE), doi=10.1109/SYSOSE.2015.7151909 , 2015.
- [6] Pu, X., Liu, L., Mei, Y., Sivathanu, S., Koh, Y., and Pu, C., "Understanding performance interference of i/o workload in virtualized cloud environments", *IEEE 3rd International Conference on Cloud Computing* (pp. 51-58). IEEE, 2010.
- [7] L. Tomás, C. Vázquez, J. Tordsson and G. Moreno, "Reducing Noisy-Neighbor Impact with a Fuzzy Affinity-Aware Scheduler," *International Conference on Cloud and Autonomic Computing*, Boston, MA, 2015, pp. 33-44., 2015.
- [8] S. Verboven, K. Vanmechelen, J. Broeckhove, "Black box scheduling for resource intensive virtual machine workloads with interference models", *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 29, no. 8, pp. 1871-1884, 2013.
- [9] R. Householder, S. Arnold, R. Green, "On cloud-based oversubscription", *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT)*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 425-431, 2014.
- [10] C. Delimitrou, C. Kozyrakis, "Quasar: Resource-Efficient and QoS-Aware Cluster Management", *Intl. Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems*, 2014.
- [11] X. Zhang, E. Tune, R. Hagmann, R. Jagal, V. Gokhale, J. Wilkes, "CPI2: CPU performance isolation for shared compute clusters", *SIGOPS European Conference on Computer Systems (EuroSys)*, pp. 379-391, 2013.
- [12] R. Nathuji, A. Kansal, A. Ghaffarkhah, "Q-clouds: Managing performance interference effects for qos-aware clouds", In *Proceedings of the 5th European conference on Computer systems* (pp. 237-250). Eurosys ACM, 2010.
- [13] Bhadauria M, McKee SA, "An approach to resource-aware co-scheduling for CMPs", *Proceedings of the 24th ACM international conference on supercomputing, ICS'10*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 189-199, 2010
- [14] Fedorova A, Seltzer M, Smith MD, "Improving performance isolation on chip multiprocessors via an operating system scheduler", *Proceedings of the 16th international conference on parallel architecture and compilation techniques, PACT'07*. IEEE Computer Society, Washington, DC, USA, pp 257-267, 2007
- [15] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, A. Courville. "Deep Learning". MIT Press, 2016.
- [16] L. Bittencourt, R. Immich, R. Sakellariou, N. Fonseca, E. Madeira, M. Curado, L. Villas, L. DaSilva, C. Lee, O. Rana. "The Internet of Things, Fog and Cloud continuum: Integration and challenges". *Internet of Things*, vol. 3 – 4, pp. 134-155, 2018.
- [17] P. Veitch, E. Curley and T. Kantecki. "Performance evaluation of cache allocation technology for NFV noisy neighbor mitigation", In *Proceedings IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, pp. 1–5, 2017.
- [18] A. Beloglazov, R. Buyya. "Managing Overloaded Hosts for Dynamic Consolidation of Virtual Machines in Cloud Data Centers under Quality of Service Constraints". In *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, vol. 24, no. 7, pp. 1366–1379, 2013.
- [19] O. Ibdunmoye, F. Hernández-Rodríguez, E. Elmroth. "Performance Anomaly Detection and Bottleneck Identification". *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 48, no. 1, 2015.
- [20] Kingma, Diederik P and Ba, Jimmy. "Adam: A method for stochastic optimization". arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980, 2014.
- [21] D. Rumelhart, G. Hinton, R. Williams. "Learning Internal Representations by Error Propagation", *Parallel Distributed Processing: Explorations in the Microstructure of Cognition*, MIT Press, vol. 1, pp. 318–362, 1986.
- [22] C. Bishop, "Neural Networks for Pattern Recognition". Oxford University Press, Inc., 1995.
- [23] A. Graves. "Supervised Sequence Labelling with Recurrent Neural Networks", *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, Springer, 2012.
- [24] S. Hochreiter, J. Schmidhuber, "Long Short-Term Memory". *Neural Computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, 1997.
- [25] Y. Le Cun, L. Jackel, B. Boser, J. Denker, H. Graf, I. Guyon, D. Henderson, R. Howard, W. Hubbard. "Handwritten digit recognition: applications of neural network chips and automatic learning", In *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 274, no. 11, pp. 41–46, 1989.
- [26] Y. Le Cun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton. "Deep learning". *Nature*, vol. 521, pp. 436–444, 2015.
- [27] Golovin, D., Solnik, B., Moitra, S., Kochanski, G., Karro, J., and Sculley, D. "Google vizier: A service for black-box optimization" *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (pp. 1487-1495). ACM, 2017.
- [28] Breiman, L. "Random forests". *Machine learning*, 45(1), 5-32, 2001.
- [29] Sun, Y.; Lo, F.P.-W. and Lo, B.. "EEG-based user identification system using 1D-convolutional long short-term memory neural networks". *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 125, p. 259-267, 2019.
- [30] Sudhakaran, S., and Lanz, O." Convolutional long short-term memory networks for recognizing first person interactions". *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision* (pp. 2339-2346), 2017.
- [31] Mozo, A., Ordozgoiti, B., and Gomez-Canaval, S. "Forecasting short-term data center network traffic load with convolutional neural networks." *PLoS one*, 13(2), e0191939, 2018.
- [32] Yanggratoke, R., Ahmed, J., Ardelius, J., Flinta, C., Johnsson, A., Gillblad, D., and Stadler, R. "Predicting real-time service-level metrics from device statistics". *IFIP/IEEE International Symposium on Integrated Network Management (IM)* (pp. 414-422), 2015.
- [33] Yanggratoke, R., Ahmed, J., Ardelius, J., Flinta, C., Johnsson, A., Gillblad, D., and Stadler, R. "Predicting service metrics for cluster-based services using real-time analytics". In *2015 11th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)* (pp. 135-143). IEEE, 2015.
- [34] Mirza, M., Sommers, J., Barford, P., and Zhu, X. "A machine learning approach to TCP throughput prediction". *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking (TON)*, 18(4), 1026-1039, 2010.
- [35] Andrzejak, L. Silva, "Using machine learning for non-intrusive modeling and prediction of software aging", *Network Operations and Management Symposium 2008. NOMS 2008*. IEEE, pp. 25-32, 2008.
- [36] J. Bogojeska, D. Lanyi, I. Giurgiu, G. Stark, D. Wiesmann, "Classifying server behavior and predicting impact of modernization actions", *Network and Service Management (CNSM), 9th International Conference*, pp. 59-66, 2013.
- [37] H. . Hlavacs, T. Treutner, "Predicting web service levels during vm live migrations", *Systems and Virtualization Management (SVM) 5th International DMTF Academic Alliance Workshop on*. IEEE, pp. 1-10, 2011.
- [38] Mushtaq, M. Sajid, Brice Augustin, and Abdelhamid Mellouk. "Empirical study based on machine learning approach to assess the QoS/QoE correlation." *17th European Conference on Networks and Optical Communications*. IEEE, 2012.
- [39] Elkotob, M., Grandlund, D., Andersson, K., and Ahlund, C. (2010, October). "Multimedia QoE optimized management using prediction and statistical learning". In *IEEE Local Computer Network Conference* (pp. 324-327). 2010
- [40] Menkovski, V., Oredope, A., Liotta, A., and Sánchez, A. C. "Predicting quality of experience in multimedia streaming. In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Advances in Mobile Computing and Multimedia* (pp. 52-59). ACM, 2009.
- [41] Machado, V. A., Silva, C. N., Oliveira, R. S., Melo, A. M., Silva, M., Francês, C. R. and Hirata, C. M. "A new proposal to provide estimation

of QoS and QoE over WiMAX networks: An approach based on computational intelligence and discrete-event simulation". In 2011 IEEE Third Latin-American Conference on Communications (pp. 1-6), 2011.

- [42] Du, H., Guo, C., Liu, Y., and Liu, Y. "Research on relationship between QoE and QoS based on BP Neural Network". IEEE International Conference on Network Infrastructure and Digital Content (pp. 312-315), 2009.
- [43] Luo, X., Liu, J., Zhang, D., and Chang, X. "A large-scale web QoS prediction scheme for the Industrial Internet of Things based on a kernel machine learning algorithm". Computer Networks, 101, 81-89, 2016.
- [44] Zhang, Y., Zheng, Z., and Lyu, M. R. "WSPred: A time-aware personalized QoS prediction framework for Web services". IEEE 22nd International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (pp. 210-219), 2011.
- [45] Abadi, M., Barham, P., Chen, J., Chen, Z., Davis, A., Dean, J., and Kudlur, M. "Tensorflow: A system for large-scale machine learning". 12th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI 16) (pp. 265-283), 2016.

areas.

SANDRA GÓMEZ-CANAVAL is an Assistant Professor at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. She obtained a M. Sc. in Software Engineering and a Ph.D. in Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Her research activity has been focused on unconventional computing models, parallel and distributed algorithms and machine learning. Her research results have been published in specialized journals and international conferences in these

...

ALBERTO MOZO is an Associate Professor at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. He obtained a M.Sc. and a Ph.D. in Computer Science from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. His current research activity is focused on network protocols and machine learning. He has been involved in the technical leadership of several research projects funded by the European Commission related to the application of machine learning to cybersecurity, network and cloud management scenarios.

ITAI SEGALL received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees from the Weizmann Institute of Science and the B.A. degree from Technion. He has joined Nokia Bell Labs, Israel, in 2014, where he is currently the Site Leader. He is also the Department Head of the Autonomous Software Systems Research team in Tel-Aviv and the Department Head of the Scalable Data Systems team in New Jersey, US. His research interests lie in software engineering and systems research, specifically in

the context of Cloud and NFV.

UDI MARGOLIN has over 35 years of experience in the software industry with focus on Network Management, Telco Cloud and Analytics. In the past 8 years Udi is a member of Nokia Software handling Architecture tasks for Nokia Cloud-band's suite, Open Source contribution, Common Software initiatives and Automation based on Analytics & Machine Learning. Prior to Nokia, Udi was a partner in Giant Steps Networks (later NG-SOFT) for 9 years delivering sophisticated custom

software solutions to leading Israeli high-tech companies in the area of Network Management leveraging Cloud technologies. Prior to that, Udi was a founder and CTO of Milestone Software (8 years), creating an Application Generator for EMS/NMS and providing solutions based on this product. Udi has vast experience in leading R&D teams, working with end customers and end to end systems integration. Udi is also leading Nokia Israel's H2020 EU project participation and took part in projects Cognet, Sonata and 5G-SOLUTIONS. Udi holds a BSc in Electrical Engineering from Tel Aviv University (1987).